

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN FIGHTING CRIME IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In today's complex environment, the issue of crime has become an urgent problem that requires multifaceted cooperation. In this sense, the creation of an effective system for combating crime and early prevention of violations in the national experience of our country in the following years is of great importance.

Key words: Complex environment, crime, effective system, methods, prevention, document, interdepartmental, commission, importance

On March 14, 2017, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the decision "On measures to further improve the system of crime prevention and combating crime". According to the document, "the work forms and methods of the state bodies implementing the prevention of crimes do not fully meet the requirements of today, primarily due to insufficient use of information and communication technologies." It was also noted that state agencies in most cases assess crime prevention as the task of law enforcement agencies only, and as a result, do not pay due attention to this activity.

According to the document, a republican interdepartmental commission on crime prevention and combating crime will be established in Uzbekistan. Juvenile Affairs Commission under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Republic of Karakalpakstan Council of Ministers, regional and Tashkent city, district (city) hokims and will be reorganized into regional interdepartmental commissions on juvenile affairs.

In addition, it was decided to establish permanent inter-departmental operational investigative teams consisting of experienced employees of the Prosecutor's Office, internal affairs and the National Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city prosecutors' offices. The document designated the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan as the sole coordinating body for the following commissions: Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Crime Prevention and Combating Crime;

Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Juvenile Affairs;

Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Human Trafficking;

Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption.

Also, every Thursday of the week has been designated as "Crime Prevention Day" and special attention is paid to the implementation of the following activities on this day: implementation of systematic measures aimed at forming a culture of intolerance to violations, ending legal nihilism, and popularizing the law-abiding behavior of citizens, including by organizing "open doors" at the bases of internal affairs bodies, law enforcement and other state agencies and organizations increase;

organization of traveling receptions of citizens and meetings of representatives of state agencies and organizations with residents in places, primarily in areas where the criminogenic situation is unacceptable, in order to thoroughly discuss the state of legality and the effectiveness of crime prevention measures;

conducting mobile court hearings on court hearings of significant social importance;

organization of house-to-house marches in order to study the socio-economic conditions of the population, to identify and eliminate the conditions that contribute to the commission of a crime;

to hear the reports of the heads of state agencies and organizations about the measures taken to prevent crimes and combat crime;

in special television and radio broadcasts, with the participation of representatives of state agencies and organizations, and the public, discussing the crime situation in places, the reasons and conditions for committing crimes, and the results of work on exposing crimes and bringing guilty persons to justice;

organization of publication of articles, comments and other materials on issues of crime prevention and crime fighting in the mass media, including the Internet global information network.

The Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan A.N. Aripov, State Adviser to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan O.B. Muradov and the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.B. Abdullayev was entrusted.

On December 1, 2017, a meeting was held in the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan with the participation of religious workers, representatives of state and public organizations, regarding the implementation of tasks related to the fight against violations and crimes and the issues of bringing the system of working with labor migrants abroad to a new level. . State adviser to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Chairman of the Youth Union of

Uzbekistan K. Kuronbayev and Chairman of the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan, Mufti Usmankhan Alimov participated in it with their reports.

At the event, the Committee on Religious Affairs under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan, the leading staff of the Center of Islamic Civilization in Uzbekistan, professors and teachers of religious educational institutions, scholars, imams, Tashkent students of Islamic Institute and Tashkent Islamic University participated.

On November 15 of this year, under the chairmanship of the President, a video selector meeting was held dedicated to the implementation of the tasks set in the prevention of violations and the fight against crime, existing problems in this regard and their solutions. Based on this, the speakers who spoke during the speeches of imams and khatibs in the places where they meet with the general population, committed a crime is a very serious sin, and the verses of the Holy Qur'an and hadiths show that such actions are strictly prohibited through live examples. The need for explanations was emphasized at the meeting.

One of the causes of crime is not knowing that what one is doing is a crime or a sin. First of all, it is necessary to fight against this ignorance. A person who knows that something is a sin will definitely turn away from it. Regardless of the type of crime, our religion is against humanity. It was specially noted that it is the duty of religious workers and intellectuals to explain that murder, theft, fraud, extortion - all these are harmful to human life.

In fact, any crime is strictly repelled in the verses of the Holy Qur'an, in the wisdom of the hadiths, and in the teachings of our great ancestors. For example, the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, called to fight against every evil and sinful act and said in the following hadith:

"If any one of you sees an evil deed, let him return it with his hand. If he is not able to do this, let him return it with his tongue. If he is not able to do that, let him return it with his tongue. But this is the weakest faith" (Narrated by Imam Muslim).

Munkar is any bad deed that is rejected in our religion. It is impossible for everyone to be indifferent when he sees every bad thing happening in his society. First of all, a person repays this sin with his own hands. Our scholars have explained that handing back a bad deed means the fight against crime by those responsible for establishing order in the society. Everyone should stop a small evil deed, but if the scale of the crime is large, the whole community should fight against it.

It is the duty of scholars, imams, intellectuals, mass media, and everyone who has the opportunity to respond to any bad deed with language. If a person cannot undo a bad deed with his hands, he does it by calling him to do good and turning him away from evil.

Also, at this meeting, on October 30 - November 9 this year, the delegation led by the State Counselor of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan met with labor migrants in the cities of Moscow, Saint Petersburg, Astrakhan and Novosibirsk of the Russian Federation. . During this trip, it was discussed at the meeting that they got to know the living and working conditions of labor migrants, that individual conversations were organized in the hostels, and that the work system of labor migrants was brought to a new level.

In fact, education of the young generation has always been the most urgent and very difficult. Our scholars have often said that the development and peace of the society depends on the education of the youth. The Honorable President said in this regard: "It is known that education of the young generation has always been important and relevant. But in the 21st century we live in, this issue is really becoming a matter of life and death."

Today, formation of faith, religion, halal and haraam, vigilance, struggle against harmful influences among young people is an urgent issue. At the meeting, Uzbek boys and girls living abroad were also warned that they are our own children, and if they are not taken care of in time, if they are indifferent, others can deceive and trap our children and make them young.

Also, in today's fast information age, the Muslim religious office, based on its goals and tasks, has expanded its activities, and at the new stage of the current reforms, has accelerated religious-educational activities, fighting ignorance with enlightenment, Islam religion. it was reported that great attention is being paid to the wide promotion of his teachings. For this purpose, it was mentioned that the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan is ready to cooperate with the editorial offices of mass media operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan in carrying out such good works.

At the end of the event, a proposal to sign a memorandum of cooperation between the Youth Union of Uzbekistan and the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan was supported in order to bring work with young people to a new level. Leading employees of mass media editorial offices, journalists, reporters of television, radio, central newspapers and websites took part in the event.

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